

PREDICTING NETWORK SECURITY USING MACHINE LEARNING

Mr. Somasekhar T Associate Professor Dept of Computer Science K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Karnataka	Moniesh S Dept of Computer Science K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Karnataka	Monika N Dept of Computer Science K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Karnataka
Pavithra R Dept of Computer Science K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Karnataka	Sindhura H Dept of Computer Science K S Institute of Technology Bengaluru, Karnataka	

ABSTRACT: A Machine Learning (ML) based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) designed to enhance cyber security by leveraging user-system interactions with potentially malicious links. The system employs a proactive approach wherein links are sent from a source system to a user system for verification. Upon receipt, the user system employs ML algorithms to analyze the link's safety. If deemed safe, the system retrieves site information for user awareness; however, if flagged as unsafe, the link provider is alerted. Furthermore, to mitigate potential risks, the system autonomously blocks the flagged website and prompts a notification to the user, safeguarding against unauthorized data collection attempts. Through this mechanism, the proposed system aims to bolster cyber security defenses by preemptively identifying and neutralizing threats posed by malicious links, thus safeguarding user privacy and system integrity.

Keywords: Machine Learning (ML), Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Cyber security, User-system interactions, Malicious links, Proactive approach, Link verification, ML algorithms, Safety analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

The project goal is to create a system dedicated to identifying malicious websites through the machine learning algorithms. This framework will encompass a broad spectrum of factors including URL-based, content-based, and server-based features, ensuring a comprehensive approach to feature extraction. In addition to extract features, the project will focus on establishing mechanisms for dataset management. This involves tasks such as gathering new data, validating the legitimacy of websites, and consistently updating the dataset to uphold its relevancy and precision. The system will accommodate several machine learning algorithms, allowing users to select the most suitable algorithm for dataset. Furthermore, the project will entail the development of a user-friendly interface for seamless interaction with the system. This interface will enable users to upload websites for analysis, review analysis outcomes, and provide feedback to improve the system's accuracy.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Title: "Privacy-Preserving Intrusion Detection in Edge Computing Using Homomorphic Encryption"

Author: Dr. Sophia Lee et al.

Published year: 2024

Description: This research proposes a privacy-preserving intrusion detection framework for edge computing environments using homomorphic encryption. The study aims to protect sensitive network data while enabling effective intrusion detection and threat mitigation at the network edge.

Methodology: The methodology involves encrypting network traffic data using homomorphic encryption techniques, allowing intrusion detection algorithms to operate on encrypted data without compromising privacy.

Result: The privacy-preserving IDS achieves effective intrusion detection while preserving data privacy, enabling secure and efficient operation of edge computing networks in various application domains.

2. Title: "A Hybrid Machine Learning Approach for Intrusion Detection in Cloud Computing Environments"

Author: Dr. Sarah Patel et al.

Published year: 2023

Description: This research presents a hybrid machine learning approach for intrusion detection in cloud computing environments. The study aims to enhance cybersecurity by effectively detecting and mitigating malicious activities within cloud infrastructures.

Methodology: The methodology involves combining supervised learning algorithms such as Random Forest and Gradient Boosting with unsupervised learning techniques like K-means clustering for anomaly detection in cloud traffic.

Result: The hybrid ML approach achieves superior detection accuracy and reduced false positives compared to traditional IDS methods, thereby enhancing security in cloud environments.

3. Title: "Deep Reinforcement Learning for Adaptive Intrusion Detection in IoT Networks"

Author: Dr. Michael Nguyen et al.

Published year: 2022

Description: This study explores the application of deep reinforcement learning (DRL) for adaptive intrusion detection in Internet of Things (IoT) networks. The research aims to develop a dynamic IDS capable of continuously learning and adapting to evolving cyber threats in IoT environments.

Methodology: The methodology involves training a DRL agent to make real-time decisions on network traffic classification and intrusion detection based on reward signals received from the environment.

Result: The DRL-based IDS demonstrates enhanced adaptability and robustness against sophisticated attacks in IoT networks, improving overall cybersecurity posture.

4. Title: "Transfer Learning-Based Intrusion Detection System for Mobile Edge Computing"

Author: Dr. Emily Chen et al.

Published year: 2021

Description: This research proposes a transfer learning-based intrusion detection system (IDS) tailored for mobile edge computing (MEC) environments. The study aims to address the unique challenges of intrusion detection in MEC

networks, such as resource constraints and dynamic network conditions.

Methodology: The methodology involves leveraging pre-trained deep learning models on large-scale datasets and fine-tuning them on smaller MEC-specific datasets using transfer learning techniques.

Result: The transfer learning-based IDS achieves improved detection performance and scalability in MEC networks, effectively mitigating security threats while minimizing computational overhead.

III. PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The suggested approach uses a web host paradigm to identify phishing websites. The model is going to be trained using a training dataset, which will be according to the classification method. The online deployment of this model will enable direct communication with the Chrome extension. The URL and website properties will be used to detect the phishing website. All of the client-side and server-side operations will be integrated into this system. A Chrome extension will be developed and integrated to the Chrome web browser on the client side, On the server, however, there will be a classifier model that has been trained using the random forest technique.

Support Vector Machine (SVM) serves as an intelligent learner within the computer industry, particularly adept at handling diverse data from various domains. Its methodology involves creating lines or planes in a high-dimensional space to effectively segregate different data clusters. The objective is to identify the hyperplane, that maximizes the margin between different groups of data. SVM employs kernel functions as specialized tools to aid in delineating these distinct lines or planes. These kernel functions, which can exhibit sigmoid, polynomial, radial basis, or linear characteristics, are instrumental in maximizing the separation between data clusters by making it as distinct as possible.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) method is used within a system for detecting intrusions to analyse link safety within the framework of machine learning (ML). Links with feature representations capture attributes such as domain repute and URL structure by using feature vectors. During training, the system associates features with either safe or harmful labels by looking through a collection of labelled links. When a new connection is received, its features are compared to those in the training dataset to perform classification. Based on the similarities in the features, Nearest Neighbors-KNN finds the 'K' most comparable linkages. The new link's classification is decided by voting for the label that has the most support among its closest neighbors.

Random Forest is an additional essential part of the suggested Intrusion Detection System (IDS). During training, several decision trees are built using the Random Forest ensemble learning technique, which yields the mean prediction (regression) or the mode of the classes (classification) for each individual tree. A random feature selection and a portion of the training set is utilized to build each decision tree in the Random Forest. This unpredictability lessens overfitting and decorrelates the trees. When used in classification or regression problems, Random Forest is able to quantify the significance of features. This enables the IDS to determine which characteristics such as URL structure and domain reputation—have the greatest bearing on whether links are safe or not. Thanks to the multiple decision average's averaging effect, it is resilient to noisy data and outliers.

IV. METHODOLOGY

➤ **Dataset Collection:** Gather a diverse and representative dataset containing labeled instances of normal network behavior and various types of intrusions. Utilize publicly available datasets and, if possible, collaborate with industry partners to ensure realism and relevance.

➤ **Data Preprocessing:** Handle missing values, normalize features, and fix any inconsistencies to clean and

preprocess the gathered dataset. This action is essential to guaranteeing the caliber and dependability of the data that is tested and used for training.

► **Feature Engineering:** Extract relevant features from the preprocessed data to characterize network traffic patterns effectively. Feature engineering may involve selecting key attributes, transforming variables, and creating new features to enhance the performance of machine learning models.

► **Model Selection:** Evaluate and choose suitable machine learning algorithms for intrusion detection, considering factors such as accuracy, interpretability, and scalability. Common choices include decision trees, random forests, support vector machines, and deep learning models.

► **Model Training:** Using the designed and preprocessed dataset, train the chosen machine learning models. Use strategies like cross-validation to optimize model hyperparameters and guarantee reliable extension to unknown data.

► **Model Evaluation:** Using different test datasets, evaluate the performance of the trained models using metrics like F1 score, ROC-AUC, precision, and recall. Iterate through the model evaluation and training procedure to optimize the system's performance.

► **User Interface:** Represents the user interacting with the system. The user uploads URLs for analysis, initiating the process of intrusion detection.

V. RESULTS

The proposed Intrusion Detection System (IDS) with a Machine Learning (ML) foundation leverages user-system interactions to enhance cybersecurity. By proactively sending potentially harmful links from a source system to a user system for verification, the IDS takes preemptive action. Upon receiving the links, the user system employs machine learning algorithms to analyze the security of the links. If the site is deemed safe, the system provides site information to the user for awareness. However, if the site is identified as harmful, the link provider is promptly notified.

Fig 5.1 Login (User)

Fig 5.2 Send Link (Intruder)

Fig 5.3 Detecting and Analyzing intruded link (User) -Safe link

Fig 5.4 Detecting and Analyzing intruded link (User) -Unsafe link

Fig 5.5 When user clicks on continue (User) -Unsafe link

Fig 5.6 When user clicks on continue (Intruder) -Unsafe link

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

To sum up, the initiative is a major step forward in the field of intrusion detection and prevention. With the use of advanced feature extraction methods and machine learning algorithms, the system can distinguish between safe and dangerous webpages with high accuracy. The project's modular architecture, which consists of parts like the Feature Extraction Module, Machine Learning Module, and User Interface Module, shows how methodical and thorough the approach to phishing detection is. When these elements are combined, parsing URLs, extracting pertinent characteristics, and classifying websites may be done quickly and effectively, which eventually results in users receiving alert alerts on time. In the long run, there is room for improvement and growth for the project. Future advancements might incorporate more machine learning algorithms, better methods for extracting features, and more user-friendly interfaces.

REFERENCES

1. Mahmoud, S. A., & Al-Dabbagh, A. M. (2018). A Review of Machine Learning Techniques for Intrusion Detection Systems. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 9(10), 134-141.
2. Wang, S. S., & Lu, Y. H. (2020). Machine Learning-Based Intrusion Detection System for Advanced Persistent Threats: A Review. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(4), 117-124.
3. Choudhary, S., Rani, R., & Kumar, V. (2021). An Intrusion Detection System Based on Machine Learning and Internet of Things. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 8(3), 1625-1633.
4. Kumar, R., Sharma, S., & Jain, V. (2019). Enhancing Cybersecurity with Machine Learning-Based Intrusion Detection Systems: A Survey. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 182(28), 20-25.
5. Elhag, I. H., Albishi, A. M., & Alabdraba, W. A. (2020). Using Machine Learning Techniques for Intrusion Detection: A Comprehensive Survey. *IEEE Access*, 8, 203498-203518.